

A STUDY ON THE ROLE OF ADVERTISEMENT ON THE PURCHASE OF ELECTRONIC GOODS

Dr. R. Thirumavalavan

Assistant Professor of Commerce,

A.V.C.College (Autonomous), Mannampandal, Mayiladuthurai – 609 305

Abstract:

Advertising is a powerful communication force and vital marketing tool helping to sell goods, services, images, and ideas through all of us receive many advertising messages daily. Now it is essential to the success of any type of business and industry. Advertising convince people to buy products. All advertising contains both information and persuasion. Advertiser's primary objective is to reach Prospective customers and influence their awareness, attitudes and buying behavior. Changing lifestyle and higher disposable income coupled with boom in the real estate and housing industry and a surge in advertising have been instrumental in bringing about a sea change in the consumer behaviour pattern.

Key Words : Advertisement, Consumer behavior.

Introduction:

Advertisement is the process of spreading product information among the potential buyer through a public medium in order to maximize sales. Such a public medium includes Newspaper, Magazines, Television, Radio and Internet.

Advertising is any form of paid non-personal presentation of ideas, goods or services for the purpose of inducing people to buy.”

Need for the study

Advertisement has proven to be a successful tool for communication but companies are still in the confusion that what kind of ingredients should be there and how do these advertisements will help to change the consumer buying behavior. It is an

important thing to know the impact of advertisement in the purchase of Home Appliances of rural women. Advertisement plays a vital role to stimulate the purchase intention of the rural buyer. The main aim of this study is to know about the impact of advertisement in behavior of buyer of home appliances.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- ↻ To identify the role of advertisement in stimulating the purchase intention.
- ↻ To study the level of impact of advertisement in purchase decision.
- ↻ To know the various factors influencing purchase of home appliances.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

1. Due to short time period researcher covers the purchase intention of rural women people during a particular time.
2. The third limitation was the sample taken by the researcher was 125 respondents only.
3. Last limitation was among the Electronic Goods only home appliances were taken.

METHODOLOGY

This study is based upon both Primary and Secondary data. A well structured questionnaire is used to collect primary data. Secondary data is collected from various sources such as books, journals, magazines, newspapers etc., the questionnaire was collected from 125 respondents of the study area. Simple random sampling technique is used for collection primary data.

Table – 1

INFLUENCE OF ADVERTISEMENT

S.No	Particulars	Frequency	Percent
1	Yes	115	92.0
2	No	10	8.0
	Total	125	100.0

Source: Primary Data

Table 1 shows that the television advertisement influences viewers to by home appliances because advertisement plays a vital role in marketing of goods. It was found that 92% of the respondents were influenced by television advertisement. 8% of the total respondents were said they were not influenced by advertisement.

Table – 2

ATTRACTIVE FEATURE

S.No	Particulars	Frequency	Percent
1	Informative	50	40.0
2	Celebrities	25	20.0
3	Theme	35	28.0
4	Others	15	12.0
	Total	125	100.0

Source: Primary Data

The above table explains about the attractive feature of the advertisement. There are four features were taken for this study they were informative, celebrities, theme of advertisement and others. 40% of the respondents were attracted by information of the advertisement, 20% were attracted by celebrities, 28% of the respondents were attracted by theme of advertisement and the other 12% were attracted by others such as Animation, graphics, etc.,

From the study it was concluded that the majority of the respondents were attracted by Information of the advertisement.

Table – 3

IMPACT OF ADVERTYISEMENT

S.No	Particulars	Frequency	Percent
1	One hour	40	32.0
2	One day	35	28.0
3	One month	5	4.0
4	Still the purchase	45	36.0
	Total	125	100.0

Source: Primary Data

Table 3 shows how long the impact advertisement stays in the minds of the respondents. 32% of the respondents were opinioned that the impact was only for one hour, 28% was opinioned that one day, 4% of the total respondents were opinioned that one month and 36% were opinioned that still the purchase of the particular product.

It was clear from this study the maximum number of respondents (36%) were opinioned that still the purchase of the particular product.

Table – 4

FACTORS OF ADVERTISEMENT

S.No	Particulars	Frequency	Percent
1	Repetitive ads	25	20.0
2	Availability of information	15	12.0
3	Demonstration	30	24.0
4	Price comparison	25	20.0
5	Brand preference	30	24.0
	Total	125	100.0

Source: Primary Data

The table 4 shows the factors of advertising that attracts the viewer to purchase the goods. Brand preference (24%) and Demonstration (24%) occupies the first place. 20% of the opinioned repetitive ads and 20% for price comparison and 12% for availability of information.

It was concluded that brand preference and demonstration plays major role in advertisement.

Table – 5

FAVORITE CELEBRITY

S.No	Particulars	Frequency	Percent
1	Yes	35	28.0
2	No	90	72.0
	Total	125	100.0

Source: Primary Data

Table 4.9 express the impact of advertisement by an celebrity who endorsing it. 72% of the respondents were said no and the remaining 28% of them said yes. It was clear that the respondents were not buy the goods if their favorite celebrity endorsing it.

It was clear that majority of the respondents (72%) were not attracted if a celebrity endorsing the advertisement.

Table – 6

QUALITY OF GOODS

S.No	Particulars	Frequency	Percent
1	Yes	115	92.0
2	No	10	8.0
	Total	125	100.0

Source: Primary Data

Table 6 answered the question whether an advertisement helps to determine the quality of goods 92% of the respondents were opinioned that advertisement helps to determine the quality of goods only 8% were said no.

It was concluded from this study advertisement is a tool helps to determine the quality of goods.

Table – 7

MODE OF DETERMINATION

S.No	Particulars	Frequency	Percent
1	Brand Image	40	32.0
2	Price	56	44.8
3	Reputation	29	23.2
	Total	125	100.0

Source: Primary Data

Table 7 reveals that how an advertisement helps to determine the quality of durable

goods. For determining quality three factors were taken for this study among them price plays the major role it occupies 44%, 32% of the respondents were determined with the help of brand image, and 23% were determined by reputation.

It was found from the study price plays a vital role in determining the quality of goods. In the study area occupies 44%.

Table – 8

USEFULNESS OF ADVERTISEMENT

S.No	Particulars	Frequency	Percent
1	Strongly Agree	30	24.0
2	Agree	80	64.0
3	Neutral	5	4.0
4	Disagree	0	0
5	Strongly disagree	10	8.0
	Total	125	100.0

Source: Primary Data

The table 8 explains the usefulness of advertisement. It was found that 64% of the respondents were agreed for usefulness of advertisement, 24% of them were strongly agree, 8% of them were strongly disagree and the remaining 4% were neutral.

The maximum number of members was agreed that advertisement is very useful for buying durable goods in the study area.

Table – 9

OVERALL SATISFACTION

S.No	Particulars	Frequency	Percent
1	Highly satisfied	55	44.0
2	Satisfied	40	32.0
3	Neutral	5	4.0
4	Dissatisfied	15	12.0
5	Highly dissatisfied	10	8.0
	Total	125	100.0

Source: Primary Data

The table 9 clearly explains the overall satisfaction of respondents regarding advertisement for home appliances. 55% of the respondents were highly satisfied, 44% of the respondents were satisfied. 12% of them were dissatisfied, 4% of the respondents were opinioned for neutral, and the remaining 8% were highly dissatisfied.

It was found from the study the maximum number of respondents (44%) was highly satisfied by the advertisement telecasting for home appliances.

SUGGESTIONS

Advertisers should try to buy time slot during entertainment programmes because majority of the respondents spend time on watching entertainment channel during prime time.

The advertisers should try to implement innovative strategies to grab attention of youth as they this age group is open to risk and is willing to try anything.

For the success of an advertising campaign with the help of the TV commercials, as for any other component of the advertising strategy, it is a must to know distinctively the tastes and the preferences of the target audience of the consumers.

CONCLUSION

The market for Home appliances is becoming more competitive now a day. Therefore, the producer of durable products should understand consumer interest much to find higher sale of their products. Television advertisement is effective in their purchase appeals and the study predicts the positive impact of television advertisement on customer attention and directly influences their interest for purchasing or to the desire for purchasing. In this study, respondents being women, it is found that women consumers attitude towards television advertisements regarding purchase of home appliances are directly related with each other.

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